
Developing Leaders to Lead Today and Tomorrow

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Abstract

This paper will appeal to leaders in all stages of their career. Whether you are just starting out in leadership, whether you have been in leadership for a number of years and want to continue in your leadership role, or whether you are a seasoned leader who wants to mentor others, this paper provides you with some takeaway tools to become a sustainable leader and to lead both today and tomorrow. There has been increasing attention on sustainability over the last couple of decades. However, when one talks about sustainability, often images of the environment, global warming and renewable energy sources, and how to ensure the environment continues long past lifetimes come to mind. However, there has also been a voice supporting research on practicing sustainable leadership in organizations. As the calendar gets closer and closer toward 2020, one questions what skills successful leaders of tomorrow need to have in order to lead effectively. This paper leans on a review of seminal and current empirical research and primary articles that identify the competencies tomorrow's leaders need. Rieckmann (2012) conducted an empirical study. The results outline twelve competencies that sustainable leaders need to be effective. The paper reviews the main sustainability core competencies identified in the study; as well as sharing information from additional literature.

Keywords: Sustainability, Leadership, Leading Tomorrow, Developing Leaders

1 Introduction

Loehr & Schwartz (2003) describe leaders as follows:

Leaders are the stewards of organizational energy...they inspire or demoralize others, first by how effectively they manage their own energy and next by how well they manage, focus, invest and renew the collective energy of those they lead. (p. 199)

The quote by Loehr and Schwartz (2003) invites the reader to consider the competencies leaders require and how organizations may develop these skills within potential future leaders. Do tomorrow's leaders have what it takes to lead? Situations today are vastly different to how they were twenty years ago. There has been increasing attention on sustainability over the past couple of decades. However, when the topic of sustainability arises, often images of the environment, global warming and renewable energy sources, and how to ensure the environment continues long past

one's lifetime come to mind. There is a voice supporting research on practicing sustainable leadership in organizations, including higher education institutions. According to Hargreaves and Fink (2007), sustainable educational leadership is something that appreciates and brings significant learning for others. They continue to say that sustainable leadership involves planning and preparing people for succession. It involves developing people to lead, long after the former leaders have gone. Dervitsiotis (2005) states that sustainable leadership is created when organizations are quicker to learn than the competition, and more adaptable than the competition. Strategies are in place to develop these.

As the clock approaches the year 2020, one questions the skills successful leaders of tomorrow need to have in order to lead effectively. The theories of leadership have not significantly changed. Instead, the situations and the world in which leaders lead have transformed enormously (Wang & Dennett, 2014). As globalization and technology evolve, so do the challenges accompanying this progress, as well as an increase in complexity and uncertainties (Rieckmann, 2012). The one size fits all style of problem solving isn't useful anymore. Rather, there is a need for creative and innovative thinking when working within complex and ambiguous situations. To quote Northouse (2016)

In recent times, upheavals in society have energized a tremendous demand for authentic leadership. The destruction on 9/11, corporate scandals...and massive failures in the banking industry have all created fear and uncertainty. People feel apprehensive and insecure about what is going on around them, and as a result, they long for bona fide leadership they can trust and for leaders who are honest and good (p.195).

The environment has evolved. It is important that there are leaders with the necessary skills to provide leadership for the future in this rapidly altering world.

The author conducted an exhaustive review of seminal and current empirical research, together with primary articles that identify the competencies tomorrow's leaders need. These findings, together with supporting literature form the foundation of this paper. Finally, the author concludes with implications for future research, followed by a discussion of generalizability.

2. Methods

Rieckmann (2012) conducted a Delphi study using experts from Germany, Great Britain, Chile, Ecuador and Mexico. A Delphi study consists of a number of questioning rounds using the experts. The experts generally answer questions in a survey. For the following round, the panel of experts receive a summary of what the experts had said; these are completely anonymous. The experts then make revisions to their original answers based on the summaries they just received. Generally the quality of the answers improve and the range of answers are narrowed down. There was convenient access to the experts within these countries. The research focused on the individual core competencies necessary to grasp the world's challenges. From there one can take it a step further and delve deeper into the ocean of leadership competencies needed for a sustainable future (Rieckmann, 2012).

The most relevant competencies identified were systemic thinking, anticipatory thinking and critical thinking. The results outline twelve competences that sustainable leaders need to be effective. This paper reviews the twelve sustainability core competencies identified in the study; as well as sharing supporting information from additional studies and literature. It should be noted that although some of Rieckmann's research findings relate to higher education, they can additionally be applied to other organizations, including business, non-profit and government. A review of additional studies and literature acknowledge these valued competencies.

The Delphi study consisted of a two-round questioning process in order to obtain the key competencies of sustainability development. Twenty four experts initially determined the categories. Then eighteen experts participated in the first round of questioning. Seventy experts participated in the next round. The questions were in English, Spanish and German. The software SPSS analyzed the data and identified twelve competencies that are outlined in Table 1.

Additionally, researchers from Ashridge University and EABIS conducted a study on the types of skills leaders of tomorrow require, as well as the mind-set necessary. One hundred and ninety four Chief executive officers and senior executives at global companies participated in the survey. This was followed by thirty three interviews. The researchers con-

cluded that there are three main factors that comprise of the mind-set future leaders need. These are: Context, complexity and connectedness. These factors are further illustrated in table 2 (Gitsham, 2009).

3. Results and Discussion

The twelve competencies identified through Rieckmann's study are illustrated in table 1.

Table 1. Rieckmann's twelve competencies.

Competencies
Systemic thinking and handling of complexity
Anticipatory thinking
Critical thinking
Acting fairly and ecologically
Cooperation in (heterogeneous) groups
Participation
Empathy and change of perspective
Interdisciplinary work
Communication and use of media
Planning and realizing innovative projects
Evaluation
Ambiguity and frustration tolerance

The competencies are further explored in this section, and at the same time connecting to additional supporting research and literature. Meanwhile the mind-set factors communicated through the studies with Ashridge University and EABIS are outlined in table 2.

Table 2. Three Clusters of Mind-Set factors.

Knowledge Skills	Description
Context	Comprehension and responsiveness to change
Complexity	Skills to handle ambiguous and low agreement situations
Connectedness	Comprehension of stakeholders outside of the organization, as well as building and maintaining relationships with external stakeholders.

(Gitsham, 2009).

The following table (3) breaks down the skills that executives agreed global leaders of tomorrow require. These are shown in percentages.

Table 3. Skills leaders need by percentage.

Percentage	Description
82%	Comprehend business risks and opportunities

88%	Adaptable mind-set and responsive to change
91%	Creativity and innovation when solving problems
73%	Ability to recognize key stakeholders
74%	Ability to understand how the company impacts the key stakeholders

(Gitsham, 2009)

Systemic thinking and handling of complexity. Systemic thinking is a combination of synthetic thinking and analytical thinking. For synthetic, it is the understanding of how parts work together and interact with each other. In comparison, analytical thinking focuses on understanding the individual parts (Tate, 2009). Therefore, leaders of today and tomorrow need to be adept at understanding how the individual parts, or individual people work or operate, and how each person or part works and operate together. The interactions of humans affect and are affected by everything around them. Leaders should understand that a change made to just one thing might impact other areas. Consequently, there may be long-term effects. Leaders may need to make additional changes based on these implications (Tate, 2009). In today’s world, situations are filled with complexity and changes. According to Gitsham (2009) “Leadership in these circumstances requires a broad mindset that is comfortable with complexity and ambiguity” (p.15). Table 3 outlines that 88% of executives agreed that leaders need to have a mind-set that is flexible and adaptable to change (Gitsham, 2009). Even as far back as 1994, Peter Senge and his colleagues started the discussion of a new mindset that leaders of that day needed to have. They discussed systems thinking, collaboration and the ability to be adaptable. They wanted leaders to create futures that were desirable. The three main parts work together to achieve that whole (Senge, Kleiner, Roberts, Ross and Smith (1994). Leaders need to be skilled at dealing with complexity and leaders should understand how a change or action made today could incur a cause and effect now, and in the long term.

Anticipatory thinking. According to Klein, Snowden and Lock Pin (2011), anticipatory thinking is the “process of imagining how unexpected events may affect plans and practice” (p.235). Anticipatory thinking should not be confused with predictions. Rather anticipatory thinking is a way to look at experiences, to blend knowledge and concepts, and to therefore provide leaders with tools to handle uncertainty and ambiguity. Anticipatory thinking is a way to plan and, if necessary alter the course of direction. It is important for leaders to consider how others may react to change or certain decisions, and therefore plan accordingly. In Gitsham’s study (2009), executives agreed that the future leaders needed to “anticipate the range of global implications that local decision making might have” (p. 23). The executives went on to say that by understanding how the organization valued the diverse make up of individuals, assisted when anticipating and responding to change. Diverse make up may include factors as age, gender, ethnicity, cultural background or religious background. These individuals with varied backgrounds and experience work together to assist in anticipating changes and problems and trying to be proactive. Global leaders face, and will continue to face uncertain challenges such as variations in culture, complexity, interdependence, vagueness, and changes (Osland, Kolb, Rubin & Turner, 2007). Although these changes pose challenges for leaders, the sustainable leaders can turn these

challenges into learning opportunities (Acutt, 2008). The learning opportunities should be shared with the team. If a new course of direction is required, the leaders must persuade the team that the new course of direction is an improved course from the one in which they are in currently. The leader comprehends that the changes they make today sustain the organization and the world in the future: The self-sustaining environment in the constantly changing society (Acutt, 2008).

Critical thinking. Marshall and Tucker (1992) discussed the role critical thinking plays in moving the organizations forward. They confirmed that organizations of the future should create systems for thinking. Every day leaders are bombarded with situations that require decisions. Critical thinking helps with decision-making. Rather than picking an answer because it feels right, leaders use critical thinking techniques to peel back the layers and to delve into the problem. They use the tools to help eliminate everything except from reliable and useful information. Leaders should create a culture where everyone learns and gains skills to think critically rather than just a select few (Dennett, 2014). A survey conducted by the American Management Association (2010) identified critical thinking as a crucial skill for leaders today, and even more importantly for leaders of the future. Over two thousand leaders (68%) said critical thinking was the most important skill for leaders. These leaders recognized that critical thinking is key to improving the organization’s bottom line. Critical thinking enhances problem- solving, decision making, as well as creating better communication and collaboration. Critical thinking can lead to improved creativity and more innovation.

To better understand their follower’s critical thinking dispositions, leaders can use the California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory to analyze and measure individual’s dispositions to critical thinking. Over twenty years of research contributed to the creation of this tool. According to the California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory, critical thinking can be divided into various subscales.

Table 4. An outline of the CCTDI subscales, together with the related descriptions.

Subscale	Description
Inquisitiveness	Curiosity and a desire to learn
Open mindedness	Being aware of own views and biases. Open to others’ views.
Systematicity	Being organized, focused and ability to have an inquiring mind.
Analyticity	Use of reasoning and the use of evidence in problem solving.
Truth seeking	Asking questions, knowledge seeking and being objective and honest.
Self-confidence	Trusting one’s own reasoning abilities
Maturity	Using judgment when making decisions or problem solving

California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory, (2013)

It is even more important in this current competitive global climate, that leaders develop their critical thinking skills in order to elevate their reasoning and problem solving abilities. By raising these competencies will help organizations to maximize their resources. It is unfortunate that by failing to develop this important critical thinking skill, organizations risk falling behind their competition (Dennett, 2014).

Acting fairly and ecologically. “You cannot move substantially towards sustainability in the absence of widely shared moral purpose” (Davies, 2007, p.66). Trust is not new but it is crucial in encouraging people to be open and honest with one another, and admitting mistakes. Yes, it is a great thing to have in an organization; however, trust is more than just a great thing to have. Trust is key to organizational success (Osland et al., 2007). When followers are well treated by their leaders, the followers in turn work hard and go beyond the leader’s expectations (Osland et al., 2007). However, on the other side, when followers are not treated well, they will exhaust valuable energy in not taking risks and working to cover their backs. Fair leaders are value driven. This is an important value when striving to improve. “Companies that look beyond maximizing wealth and profits, and are driven by values and a sense of purpose, out-perform companies that focus only on short-term gain” (p. 133). The values drive decision-making and problem solving (Davies, 2007). Employees are treated with equity and fairness.

One of the most recent theory of leadership is authentic leadership. This questions whether leadership is genuine and real (Northouse, 2016). There is a need for trustworthy leaders who are ethical and honest. Although there are a number of definitions of authentic leadership, there is not one commonly agreed definition. However there is an approach to authentic leadership. George (2003) conducted interviews with 125 leaders. George also reflected on his own experience as a corporate executive. As a result, George learned that authentic leaders are similar to servant leaders in that they want to serve others. These authentic leaders have a strong understanding of themselves and they use their core values as a foundation to lead. He found that these leaders have five characteristics that are shown in table 6.

Table 6. Characteristics of Authentic Leaders

Number	Description of Characteristic
1	Comprehend their purpose
2	Possess strong values
3	Create trusting relationships
4	Demonstrate self-discipline
5	Passionate about their mission

George (2003)

During the extensive interviews, George (2003) learned that authentic leaders possess a comprehensive understanding of their purpose. They know exactly what they are meant to do in life. They have a genuine passion about their goals. They do not need to be externally motivated to achieve their goals, rather they are motivated by intrinsic reasons. These leaders also treat others based on their personal value system. Decisions

are made based on this strong value system. George found that authentic leaders wear their hearts on their sleeves. They are open and honest with others. This helps to form relationships and establishes trust. Authentic leaders are very focused and have a solid self-discipline. They use this personal discipline to work toward and achieve their goals. They are not un-predictable and this helps people to know how to approach these leaders, resulting in good communication. People feel a strong sense of security with this approach. Authentic leaders (according to George) are sensitive and empathetic to others. They are genuinely compassionate. Initially by being open and honest, and sharing and listening to stories encourages authenticity and develops compassion.

Leaders can measure their level of authentic leadership using the Authentic Leadership Questionnaire developed by Walumbwa, Avolio, Gardner, Wernsing and Peterson (2008). The questionnaire was validated and studies found there was a positive correlation to performance, followers’ satisfaction with supervisors, organizational citizenship and organizational commitment. The sixteen questions will assist the leader in assessing their own approach to leadership and in ways to work on their approach.

Social just leaders not only see themselves as being professional, but also as responsible people of the local community. They are simply good and ethical human beings. Burns (1978) defined moral leadership as followers and leaders working toward the same goals, values and needs. The relationship between supervisor and employee is not emphasized, rather the shared purpose is emphasized. Leaders do what they say they are going to do, and if they make certain promises relating to change, they take accountability of those promises. Sustainable leaders must maintain their ethical standards when leading in this ever-changing world and environment. Leaders of tomorrow must understand the ethical foundation upon which their decisions are formed (Gitsham, 2009).

Cooperation in (heterogeneous) groups. Leaders that lead today and tomorrow provide opportunities for the followers to collaborate, to share, to explore, to learn, and to generate their own solutions to challenges. These leaders genuinely consider the greater good and want to hear from others, as well as listen to others’ ideas. These leaders establish systems and cultures to encourage and invite idea sharing. These leaders do not always have to be right. Rather than telling others how to solve a problem, these leaders provide opportunities for sharing knowledge, for generating new ideas, and for exploring alternatives (Ferdig & Ludema, 2005). According to Senge et. al. (1994):

It is helpful to have a reason to talk and learn – a situation that compels deliberation, a need to solve a problem, the collective desire to create something new, or a drive to foster new relationships with other parts of the organization (p.356).

Organizations are made up of unique individuals that may or may not speak a common language. It is important therefore, that opportunities exist for these unique individuals to collaborate and communicate with like and unlike minded people in the organization. Senge et. al. (1994) continue to stress the importance of planned learning within organizations. In uncertain and ambiguous situations where the answer is not clear, it is necessary to be honest and to acknowledge the uncertainty, and to admit that the answers are not known. It is necessary to share with the group and to create that platform for learning, and for solving the uncertain problems together.

Participation. Wagner and Gooding (1987) define participation or participative leadership as making decisions jointly, or as a superior and a subordinate sharing the influence through the reporting structure of the organization. According to Northouse (2016),

Participative leadership consists of inviting followers to share in the decision-making. A participative leader consults with followers, obtains their ideas and opinions, and integrates their suggestions into the decisions about how the group or organization will proceed (p. 118).

Leaders encourage others to think of new ideas and to be willing to share these ideas. These leaders create an environment that encourages people to take risks and to participate in decision-making and problem solving. People are empowered to think (Sagnak, 2016).

A study of eight hundred and fifty teachers suggested that participation enhances intrinsic motivation and correlates with change organizational citizenship behavior. The study found that participatory leadership was a significant predictor in change organizational citizenship behavior. Organ (1988) defined organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as “individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization” (p. 4). Participatory leaders create learning organizations and invite innovation (Wagner & Gooding, 1987). Employees are asked to contribute with their suggestions and recommendations, as well as being involved by providing their opinions (Chen & Tjosvold, 2006). The environment is such that employees feel they can express their ideas and thoughts freely, and these ideas at times contribute to decision making within the organization. Leaders that encourage and demonstrate participative leadership invite creative and innovative thinking. They set the stage for this type of interaction to play out. It can be said that participatory leaders contribute to the effectiveness of the organizations (Sagnak, 2016).

Empathy and change of perspective. Stated by Machiavelli (1961) in *The Prince*,

It must be realized that there is nothing more difficult to plan, more uncertain of success, or more dangerous to manage than the establishment of a new order of things; for he who introduces change makes enemies of all those who derived advantage from the old order and finds but lukewarm defenders among those who stand to gain from the new one (p.27).

Sustainable leaders need to create the field of play where there is not a victor and a loser; rather where people can talk about their differences of opinions openly and in a trusting environment. Where the thought of change does not create high barriers of walls of resistance. People unite in their desire for a positive outcome as a result of change. However, sustainable leaders should still recognize the symbols and traditions of the organization. Leaders of tomorrow must recognize the culture of yesterday.

Robert Greenleaf first articulated the characteristics of a Servant Leader. In his seminal essay in 1970, he stated that the ideal leaders were servants first. These leaders put the needs of their followers before the needs of their own. Spears (2002) further outlined that empathy was one of the ten characteristics in the well-known writings of Greenleaf.

To quote Spears (2002)

Empathy is standing in the shoes of another person and attempting to see the world from that person's point of view. Empathetic servant leaders

demonstrate that they truly understand what followers are thinking and feeling. When a servant leader shows empathy, it is confirming and validating for the follower. It makes the follower feel unique (p. 227).

Interdisciplinary work. Tomorrow's leader must understand the butterfly effect. Merriam-Webster defines the butterfly effect as small changes in the beginning of a condition that can create future unpredictable situations of a larger scale. Not all connections occur as one incident; instead, they are linked to other actions. Our naked eyes may not see these actions. However, they are there, always changing. The world constantly changes. Organizations and communities are complex systems filled with layers of actions and effects. Each action we make incurs an effect. By being aware of these linkages help to broaden the leader's knowledge, to strengthen partnerships both within the organization and out in the community (Ferdig, 2007).

In his report on developing the global leader, Gitsham (2009) highlighted that future leaders should realize the interdependency of actions and how these can affect a larger picture. Fink (2003) describes interdisciplinary as “different kinds of information, perspectives, and methods of inquiry and analysis—all in order to develop a more holistic understanding of a problem or issue” (p. 43). Leaders who lead today and into the future need to have the skillset to draw from knowledge from different disciplines and areas of expertise. These leaders view situations through multiple perspectives (Rhodes, 2010).

Navigating the permanent whitewater of the rapidly changing world requires leaders and leadership educators who can integrate theory and application, scholarship and intuition, and tradition and innovation (Vaill, 1996).

Communication and use of media. Collins (2001) states that leaders should promote and develop strategic conversations within the organization. These conversations can be both informal and formal. He continues to say that by having these discussions, creates a common language, and a comprehension of how people can actually make a difference. By keeping everyone in the loop, and by communicating a vision, helps to move everyone forward in the same direction. Gitsham (2009) shared findings of his study that 75% of executives believed that future leaders should have a mind-set of connectedness. These leaders also needed to have the ability to communicate with a variety of stakeholders (including internal and external stakeholders). They should comprehend the context of the changing business environment, and in turn communicate the rationale for creating certain objectives. They must explain the reasoning for going after certain social and environmental objectives.

Effectively communicating a clear vision is important in leading today and tomorrow. Meriam Webster's Dictionary defines visionary as “A person of strong and creative imaginative power and, often, the ability to inspire others”. Sander (2012) pairs passion and vision. Leaders that have vision but not passion will find it difficult to motivate their followers. Leaders with passion but no vision will struggle to lead its followers on a strong and clear path to success. These leaders understand how a common understanding can lead to positive outcomes for the greater good.

Planning and realizing innovative projects. According to Ferdig and Ludema (2005), often innovations and new ways of thinking are a result of experiences of actually going through a change, as well as going through the chaos the change creates. These innovations invite a new energy into organizations. Quoting Sander (2012) “Good leadership requires good innovation; without it, you aren't really leading, but rather fighting

a rearguard action in the marketplace” (p.102). Leaders of today and tomorrow are pioneers of learning, and they have a natural love for inquiry. They experiment without the fear of making a mistake. Rather they learn from mistakes and share what they have learned with others. These leaders cultivate a culture of inquiry. They share even when the outcomes of their actions do not turn out as expected. They create a climate of sharing and one where people are not afraid to take risks and act as pioneers. Leaders of tomorrow are not ashamed to learn from their mistakes (Ferdig, 2007).

Evaluation. Davies (2007) suggests developing strategic measures of success by viewing staff as reflective practitioners. These practitioners establish learning communities by making the time to discuss ideas. Gitsham (2009) stressed the importance of converting learning from external stakeholders to realistic situations within the organization. Rowden (2007) posits the importance of supporting others to think and reflect on their experiences, and to learn from them. He emphasizes leaders should encourage an environment that invites others to learn from their mistakes. He continues to say that they should consider how they might even make their capabilities for learning even better, and how they may share what they have learned with the organization.

A method to share and reflect on learning is with Kolb’s Experiential Learning Model. This model forms its foundations on its belief that learning is based on four steps. These steps include a concrete abstract dimension as well as a reflective abstract dimension. Participants initially observe and reflect on an experience in order to process understanding. They assimilate this information and create potential actions to take and then decide on a particular action to take. Leaders may utilize the Kolb’s Experiential Learning Model within organizational problem solving. The four steps of the model are outlined in the following table.

Table 5. Kolb’s Experiential Learning Model

Dimension	Description
Concrete Experience (CE)	Employs experience
Abstract Conceptualization (AC)	Based on rationality and logic
Reflective Observation (RO)	Considers information from different viewpoints
Active Experimental (AK)	Needs hands-on learning

Ambiguity and frustration tolerance. When using the term ‘resilience’ means the ability to deal with the stressors and to manage day to day challenges and pressure. To quote the definition from Merriam and Webster, “resilience is the ability to recover from or adjust easily from misfortune”. The ability to learn from mistakes (Brooks, 2005). Davies (2007) describes resilience as:

Within particular changing and environments, resilience encompasses the individual’s capacity to deal effectively with stress and pressure, to cope with everyday challenges, to rebound from disappointments, mistakes and adversity, to develop clear and realistic goals, to solve problems, to interact comfortably with others, to treat oneself and others with respect and dignity, and to have the ability to meet life’s challenges with thoughtfulness, confidence, purpose, responsibility, empathy and hope (p. 68-69).

According to Halpin (2003), resilience also means being hopeful, as well as possessing a positive mindset. Grit is another term used when talking about the topic of resilience. Duckworth (2016) describes grit as the way one continues to persevere for goals in the long-term, while engaging in passion. To quote the words of Duckworth (2016) “If you’re a leader, and you want the people in your organization to be grittier, create a gritty culture” (p.245). Grit can be learned, according to Duckworth (2016). Leaders can use tools to assist in learning about their levels of grit or resiliency, as well as their followers. Leaders can guide others to build and grow their personal levels of grit. There are a variety of instruments leaders can use to measure grit or resiliency. Duckworth (2016) developed the Grit Scale I to measure levels of grit. Questions focused on passion and perseverance. Participants determined both their individual levels as well as a total score. Components include questions on distractions, how participants deal with setbacks and focus.

Hargreaves and Fink (2007) reiterate the importance of ensuring that leaders who are responsible for continuous improvement in their organizations are not worn out. Strive for sustainable improvement; while at the same time sustain these leaders of improvement. This concurs with Boyzatis, Smith and Blaize’s (2006) article regarding the effect stress has on leadership. Even effective leaders, when experiencing chronic power stress over time, can result in having their adaptability, health and ability to learn, impaired. Therefore, their successful leadership is not sustained.

Sustainable leadership also includes not only having the right leaders in the right place, but also ensuring they develop leaders to continue their success and, who can grow even stronger when existing leaders depart the organization. Collins (2001) reviewed companies that boasted good performance with those that boasted great performance. Some themes emerged from these studies: The importance of additional executive leaders who can create and build ‘enduring greatness’. Collins described these leaders as those who not only contribute to the organization’s success but also how many leaders they leave behind who can go even further. He confirmed the notion of having the right people in the right places. These leaders are skilled and able to develop the themes. Also worth mentioning is the ability to concentrate on the data with a view to make improvements. Collins discussed ‘The Hedgehog Effect’. Hedgehogs are known for their immense concentration. A sustainable leader has this concentration through their own motivation and energy, as well as the ability to put the right people in the right places for various tasks. This focus keeps the leaders and the organizations continuing successfully. Hargreaves and Fink (2007) describe sustainable educational leadership as something that savors and creates significant learning for others. It is beneficial for everyone in today’s world, and in the world to come.

4. Conclusion

So, is it possible to generalize from these results? Although the findings of Rieckmann’s study were based upon the results of the experts in certain countries and therefore somewhat limited, these findings should not be taken lightly. The author included an extensive review of seminal and current empirical research, together with primary articles that supported Rieckmann’s findings. There is significant literature that agrees with the competencies that Rieckmann identified. There is significant agreement that the world has changed and it is continuing to evolve, and there are certain skills needed in order to lead into the future. Therefore, this is a start. Sustainable leaders can be developed. Leaders can build on the competencies identified in this paper. Leaders can develop these skills

within their successors so that the right leadership may continue even when the original leader is no longer there. This knowledge can assist human resource and development professionals when developing training programs and developing talent. Higher Education institutions can use this knowledge to develop curricula in order to develop these future leaders. The literature implies that the world is moving in the right direction and is recognizing some of the key skills needed for today and tomorrow's leader.

While this paper serves as a solid foundation of the competencies required for sustainable leadership, the author recognizes that further research should be conducted. Studies using a wider population situated in a more broad range of countries that do not exclude the United States. Incorporate findings from research conducted in a variety of organizations on defining the skills that a leader needs to lead both today and tomorrow. As Wang and Dennett (2014) mentioned earlier in the paper, the theories have not significantly changed, rather the surrounding situations in which the leaders lead have changed. Sustainable leadership ensures there is a steady pipeline of leaders to keep the waters of continuous improvement flowing (Hargreaves and Fink, 2007).

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